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The Inscriptions of the Church Utensils of Tatev Monastery (Republic of Armenia, Region of Syunik)

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The written sources of the history of famous spiritual and cultural center of Tatev monastery of medieval Armenia (at present in the Syunik region of Republic of Armenia) aren't only the epigraphs and colophons of manuscripts, but also the inscriptions of various church artefacts. Some of them are kept in the History museum of Armenia and were studied at the beginning of 1960's yet. 10 inscribed copper plates kept in the Tatev monastery didn't deserve of special attention till today. The inscriptions of plates, which are dated to second half of the 18th century are short memories, in which are testified the names of donators, the monastery which received donations and the clagymans who moved the items. The plates are remarkable with its round stamp-marks of masters or workshops, which are kept on the external side of the bottom and are decorated with crosses, almonds and floral ornaments. At present 2 of them are exhibited in the newly-opened museum of Tatev monastery.

Arsen Harutyunyan

Inscripții comemorative pe vesela bisericească a mănăstirii Tatev (Republica Armenia, regiunea Syunik)

Izvoare scrise pimate ale renumitului centru spiritual și cultural al Armeniei medievale – mănăstirea Tatev (azi în regiunea Syunik, Republica Armenia), sunt nu numai texte epigrafice și inscripții comemorative pe cărțile manuscrise, dar și inscripții pe o varietate de veselă cu caracter religios. O parte a acestor obiecte se păstrează în Muzeul de Istorie a Armeniei și a fost studiată încă la începutul anilor 60 ai secolului trecut, dar 10 platouri din aramă aflate în mănăstire au rămas în afara atenției cercetătorilor. Textele gravate pe platouri, care datează din a doua jumătate a secolului XVIII, prezintă scurte inscripții comemorative în care sunt documentate numele donatorilor, a celor care au recepționat donația, sau al preoților care au transmis obiectul. Platourile sunt valoroase și prin prezența în partea exterioară a bazelor a ștanțelor de formă cruciformă, de migdale sau florale a meșterului sau atelierului producător. Două dintre ele sunt expuse în muzeul recent deschis în incinta mănăstirii Tatev.

Арсен Арутюнян

Памятные надписи церковной утвари Татевского монастыря (Республика Армения, область Сюник)

Письменными первоисточниками знаменательного духовного и культурного центра средневековой Армении, Татевского монастыря (современная область Сюник Республики Армения), являются не только данные эпиграфики и памятные записи рукописных книг, но и надписи на разнообразных предметах церковной утвари. Некоторая часть этих предметов хранится в Музее истории Армении и изучалась еще в начале 1960-ых, однако находящиеся в храме 10 медных тарелей с памятными надписями не удостоивались особо внимания исследователей. Гравировки на датированных второй половиной XVIII века тарелях являются краткими памятными надписями, в которых засвидетельствованы имена дарителей, принимающих дар монастыря, передающих предмет священнослужителей. Тарели примечательны сохранившимися на внешней стороне основания крестообразными, миндалевидными или исполненными в виде цветка округлыми печатями (знаками) мастера-медника либо данной мастерской. Два из этих предметов в настоящее время выставляются в музее, открытом недавно при Татевском монастыре.

Historical overview

Tatev monastery is one of the most famous spiritual and cultural centers of medieval Armenia (fig. 1), where according to legend during the preaching of Christianity was martyred Yevstaeus who was a pupil of St. Thaddeus the Apostle (Smbatean 1930, 278). According to historiographer Step'anos Orbelyan, since 4-5th centuries

on the same place there was a church, which was built of dull and uncut stones, where shivered not many monks (Orbelean 1861, 148). Becoming the seat of the Syunik episcopate from the end of the 8th century Tatev monastery obtained new estates through purchases and donations, such as villages, farms, lands etc. In 848 the prince of Syunik Philippe adjacent to the old church built one nave basilica

Fig. 1. The general view of Tatev monastery from south-west (2015)

church of St. Gregory the Illuminator (Orbelean 1861, 154). At the end of the 9th century on the place of old church was built the general temple of St. Paul and St. Peter (895-906) by initiative of Bishop Hovhannes and with the help a group of princes of Syunik (Orbelean 1861, 162-163; Yakobson 1947, 304). It should be noted, that Armenian king Smbat I Bagratuni, catholicos Havhannes V Draskhanakerttsi, as well as a visible princes and spirituals of Syunik participated in the solemn opening of the temple (Orbelean 1861, 165). In 930 by initiative of Bishop Hakob Dvinetsi of Syunik and by masters probably invited from Italy the walls of temple are painted (Manukyan 2015, 317). The study of preserved details of frescoes turned that they are pictorially typical in Western European art (Thierry 1968, 242; Durnovo 1979, 148).

Tatev monastery, which became educational and writing center since 9th century was more famous in the 14-15th centuries, when by initiative of Hovhan Vorotnetsi and Grigor Tatevatsi was founded high school-university in the monastery. During this period a numerous manuscripts are copied in this scriptorium, scribes of which are pupils of the local school (Gevorgian 2003, 156-170). Tatev didn't lose its former glory and importance in the 17-18th centuries too. During the reign of Movses Tatevatsi (1629-1633) and future catholicoses the monastery continued to be active, having about 500 members of monastic congrega-

tion. The construction of the monastic, economic and other auxiliary buildings, which are attached to the fortress, testifies about a large congregation of monastery (Ter-Movsisean 1938, 20-21).

The written sources of the monastery

The reliable sources of the history of monastic complex are colophons of manuscripts and about 300 epigraphs¹, which are kept on the ancient walls of the monastic buildings and other monuments – khachkars (cross-stones) and tombstones. Besides them for the study of the history of the 17-18th centuries of abovementioned religion center is remarkable also the collection of the church inscribed utensils (pix-cover, silver cross, ephod, incense box, stole, cymbals, plate, chasuble, chalice etc.), most of which were moved to the History museum of Armenia during the Soviet period. Previously they were studied and published by the researcher of museum Yevgine Musheghyan. In the catalog of inscribed church artefacts of the museum's collection there are 28 different utensils and other items from Tatev monastery, the earliest of which is a wooden door of the St. Gregory the Illuminator church, which is dated to 1253. Other items, which dedicated to the Tatev monastery are mostly dated to the 18th

1. Only 93 epigraphs from Tatev monastery are published in the 2nd volume of "Corpus of Armenian Epigraphs" (Barkhudaryan 1960, 13-39). Earlier 146 epigraphs are published by Archbishop Mesrop Magistros Ter-Movsisyan (Ter-Movsisyan 138, 44-53).

Fig. 2. a-b. The plates, which are exhibited in the newly-opened museum of Tatev monastery (2019)

century (Musheghyan 1964). It is interesting, that according to inscription of one of the silver blessing cross, in 1751 it was dedicated to the St. Astvatsatsin church of Tatev's Mets (Big) hermitage («ի դուռն Դաթելու Մեծ անապատին, որ է Սր. Աստուածածնա»), in memory of mahtesi² Dovlat and Ohan (Musheghyan 1964, 71₄₅). According to another inscription of the silver clasp of chasuble, in 1768 it was dedicated to the St. Minas church of Tatev village («...էտ Դաթելոյ զեղին Սր. Մինասայ եկեղեցուն»), in happy memory of Margar's son Khosrov, who was from Aghandz village (Musheghyan 1964, 150₂₈₄).

It should be noted, that property dedicated to the monasteries and churches (manuscript, curtain, utensils etc.) was usually inscribed³. The main reason was the expectation of donators to deserve for mentioning and their soul's salvation, due to which regardless of the type of subject, the written "formula" of mentioning is almost the same. (Harutyunyan 2019, 319-320). The nice proof of this are numerous

copper plates discovered in the basement of Etchmiadzin printing house in 1896, 1613 of which had Armenian inscriptions (Hakobyan 1990, 81). In the inscriptions of the copper utensils of the Armenian Ethnographic museum of Sardarapat, for expectation of memory the donators dedicated different donations to the St. Hakobyants monastery of Jerusalem, St. Astvatsatsin church of Etchmiadzin, St. Step'anos church of Arzakan (Kotayk region of Republic of Armenia), St. Sargis church of Khoy town (at present in Iran), St. Grigor of Masiros village (province of Van, in Turkey) (Harutyunyan, Babajanyan 2019, 1424, 145-148₁₁₋₁₄). According to another inscription, which is preserved on the copper pitcher in the museum of St. Astvatsatsin church of Budapest, it was dedicated to the St. Hakob church of Opum village (Opyun, province of Diarbekir, in Turkey) (Harutyunyan, Khudanyan 2016, 145₁₄).

The collection of the copper plates of Tatev monastery

During our archaeological and epigraphical investigations of Tatev monastery and surrounding monuments (since 2014) turned out that in monastery are kept the collection of inscribed copper plates which were dedicated to the monastery in the second half of the 18th century by different donators. Those are 10, 2 of which since October 2019 are exhibited in the newly-opened museum of monastery⁴ (fig. 2a, b).

2. Mahtesi title means the pilgrim who went to the tomb of Christ in Jerusalem.

3. In general, the material of museums rich in inscribed samples of household and church artefacts is more or less known to science from different exhibitions (also in abroad) and published catalogs (Ghazaryan 1984; Hovhannisyan 1997; Ayvazyan et al. 2007; Poghosyan et al. 2008; Tokmajean 2016). In separate exhibits are also rich the collections of Hermitage museum (Saint Peterburg), the Catholicosate of Cilikia of Antelias, the Armenian patriarchates of Jerusalem and Constantinopol, the museum of primacy of Aleppo, the museum of St. Astvatsatsin church of Budapest and other spiritual-cultural centers.

4. After renovation of the previously stud, which attached to the northern entrance of the fortress of monastery and aux-

The epigraphist Grigor Grigoryan in his archival materials also mentioned about inscribed plates collection of Tatev monastery. According to him the plates are 6 and were found in 1980. Grigoryan deciphered the inscriptions of plates, 2 of which aren't in our collection. One of them was dedicated to the Tatev monastery in memory of some Sargis, another in memory of mahtesi Grigor, both are dated 1776.

a. Յ[Ի]Շ[Ա]Տ[Ա]Կ Է ՍԱՐ[Գ]ԻՍԻՆ, Ի Դ[ՈՒ]ՆՆ ՏԱԹԵԻՈՒ ՎԱՆԻՑՆ, ՁԵՌԱՄԲ ՕՎՍԷՓ Վ[Ա]ՐԴ[Ա]ՊԵՏԻՆ, ԹՎ[ԻՆ] ՌՄԻԵ.-ԻՆ (1776):

In memory of Sargis, to the Tatev monastery, by Vardapet (Archimandrite) Ovsep', in 1776.

b. Յ[Ի]Շ[Ա]Տ[Ա]Կ Է Մ[Ա]Հ[ՏԵՍ]Ի ԳՐԻԳՈՐԻՆ, Ի Դ[ՈՒ]ՆՆ ՏԱԴԵՈՒ ՎԱՆԻՑ, Ձ[Ե]Ռ[ԱՄ]Բ ՕՎՍԷՓ Վ[Ա]ՐԴ[Ա]ՊԵՏԻՆ, ԹՎ[ԻՆ] ՌՄԻԵ. (1776):

In memory of mahtesi Grigor, to the Tatev monastery, by Vardapet Ovsep', in 1776⁵.

There is a one plate from Tatev monastery in the collection of History museum of Armenia, which undoubtedly was a part of the same group.

c. Յ[Ի]Շ[Ա]Տ[Ա]Կ Է ԱԿՈԲԻՆ, Ի Դ[ՈՒ]ՆՆ ՏԱԴԵՈՒ ՎԱՆԻՑ, ՁԵՌ[ԱՄ]Բ ՈՎՍԷՓ Վ[Ա]ՐԴ[Ա]ՊԵՏԻՆ, ԹՎ[ԻՆ] ՌՄԻԵ. (1776) (Musheghyan 1964, 141₂₄₆).

In memory of Akob, to the Tatev monastery, by Vardapet Ovsep', in 1776.

Vardapet Ovsep', whose name was evidenced at the end of the abovementioned inscriptions was a legate or one of the clergymans of Tatev monastery, who for some reason went to another place (perhaps a city), where the donators, mentioned

iliary buildings of the western part of the same fortress some halls have been turned into museum, where are exhibited some khachkars (cross-stones) of yard, one of the copper bells named after Step'anos Orbelyan, the copies of the manuscripts written in Tatev monastery and other cultural values. The coordination of the exhibits of the museum was carried out with our consultation by Priest Sevak Saribekyan, the director of the "Ruben Sevak" art museum of Mother See of Holy Etchmiadzin, to whom I would like to express my gratitude for the opportunity to study the objects and to take photos.

5. Epigraphist Grigor Grigoryan of happy memory planned to compile an additional volume of "Corpus of Armenian Epigraphy" containing the epigraphs of historical Syunik, which remained incomplete but were preserved – the letters reduced by the carver and restored by us are indicated.

in the inscriptions, sent with him the plates to the Tatev monastery as a gift. The uniformity of inscriptions and identity of dates testified about the donations, which carried out by the residents of the same settlement, by which dictation were compiled the inscriptions too⁶. There are a numerous examples not only about donations of plates, but also about manuscripts, old printing books, covers, dressing etc., which were dedicated to the monasteries or churches by legates or clergymans. On different occasions being in the Armenian colonies and enjoying the trust and sympathy of the local people legates or clergymans moved the donations to the St. Etchmiadzin or other Armenian famous spiritual center (in this case to the Tatev monastery). For that reason, the names of legates or clergymans transferring the donations, sometimes were mentioned on the donated artefacts (Malkhasyan 2011, 13, 52, 54, 58, 69 etc.).

Unlike to our assumption Yevgine Musheghyan the title of vardapet, which are mentioned at the end of inscriptions, considered as a copper-smith. According to some inscriptions of plates from History museum of Armenia she wants to substantiate the idea, according to which in the 18th century the copper-smiths, who acted mostly in Tokhat⁷, were called as a vardpet, varpet or vardapet. For instance, Musheghyan mentioned the names of masters Ohan, Agheksandr and Ghazar⁸, who acted in Tokhat noticing that on the own plates inscriptions Agheksandr was remembered as a varpet, vardpet and vardapet (Musheghyan 1964, 6). So, in this context the word "ձեռամբ" (by) means not "dedicated by", but "ձեռամբ շինեցաւ" (made by). For instance, the inscription of the binding of Gospel of silver-plated of Grigor Tuments is the following. «Յիշատակ է արծաթապատ Աւետարանս Տիրամայր Սբ. Աստուածածնին, շինեցաւ ձեռամբ խօճայ Թումենց Գրիգորին. ամէն, թվին ՌՄԺԷ.

6. Our colleague, expert in Arabic Mihran Minasyan prompted us about this version (11. 07. 2020).

7. The centers of copperworks in the 18-19th centuries were also Kesaria, Sebastia, Kars, Van, Jugha, Yernzka, Aleksandrapol (at present Gyumri), where the copper-smiths made household and church utensils satisfying the several requirements of population (Poghosyan et al. 2008, 11).

8. During the repair works of old Apartments of catholicos of St. Etchmiadzin carried out the archaeological excavations (by N. Hakobyan), at which time was found a copper plate with the name of Ghazar Vardapet (Harutyunyan 2016, 68₄₃).

(1768)» (Malkhasyan 2011, 36-37) (This silver-plated Gospel in memory of Tiramayr (Holy Mother of God) St. Astvatsatsin church, which made by khoja (merchant) Tuments Grigor, in 1768).

In our opinion, both in epigraphs and in metal items inscriptions the word “vardapet” mostly is abbreviated, such as վրդտ (vrtdt), վրդպտ (vrpdt), վրպտ (vrpt), which according to content we can decipher as a “vardapet” (archimandrite). Perhaps, the reason of this confusion is a not correct decipherment, according to which Yevgine Musheghyan the clargymans mentioning in the inscriptions considered as a masters of utensils. Moreover, in the inscriptions of household and church utensils known to us, the masters usually didn't mention themselves by name, but they were satisfied only with the master's stamp-marks, which are preserved on the bottoms of plates or sometimes with the stamp-marks containing the abbreviated name of masters (Harutyunyan, Babajanyan 2019, 145₁₀).

Compiling the inscriptions of plates, the engraver used ligatures and abbreviations which are typical in epigraphs. The vowel contractions are

mentioned with small horizontal particles. For example, due to that trick turned out that Ovsep' is mentioned as a vardapet, because there are small particles in the place of two a (u) letters. By the same way also are mentioned the letters of date. The beginning and the end of the inscriptions are mentioned with similar vegetal ornaments. More interesting are stamp-marks of masters, which are stamped on the external side of plate's bottoms. On the plates mentioning the name of Ovsep' Vardapet there are round stamps, which are decorated with crosses, according to which we can be assumed that they are the personal stamp-marks of the same master (fig. 3a-c). Other 4 plates are made by two different masters, 2 of them there are stamps with almonds, another 2 with the floral ornaments (fig. 4a-c).

Two plates from our collection have a uniform inscriptions so below we will present only 8. The similar shaped wares present shallow plates or bowls with a proto-conical profile, having a low ring-form bottom and a pronounced flat rim. The bowls are coated with a tin layer, occasionally worn out. The simple decoration consists of engraved linear ornaments. The bowls bear master's

Fig. 3 a-c. The stamp-marks of masters decorated with crosses.

Fig. 4 a-c. Other stamp-marks of masters.

or workshop's stampmarks on the external side of the bottom. Considering the similarity of these wares we will present only their sizes, technical condition and decipherment of inscriptions. One

1. Copper plate, diameter 17 cm, diameter of bottom 10 cm, height 3.5 cm.

Condition – The body of plate is gap from bottom. It is inclined.

Inscription – On the external side of rim, carved and convex letters, 1 line.

Յ[Ի]Շ[Ա]Տ[Ա]Կ Է ԳՐԻԳՈՐԻ ՈՐԴԻ ՂՈՒԿԱՍ, Ի Դ[ՈՒ]ՆՆ ՏԱԹԵՒՈՒ ՎԱՆԻՑ,
ՌՄԻԴ. (1775):

In memory of Grigor's son Ghukas, to the
Tatev monastery, in 1775.

In collection there is a one plate with the same inscription too. In fact, that the inscription was compiled by two several engravers. At first was an only convex part, which was later used in the text of the carved inscription. Two different writing and time of inscriptions usually are considered the memories of first and second donators (Musheghyan 1964, 6), while in this case there isn't second name, so owner of plate Grigor's son Ghukas it was dedicated to the Tatev monastery in 1775, accordingly, the date and name of the monastery were added on the plate as a monastery, which received the donation.

2. Copper plate, diameter 19 cm, diameter of bottom 10.5 cm, height 5 cm.

Condition – The body of plate is gap from bottom. It is inclined. The tin layer partly eroded.

Inscription – On the rim, carved letters, 1 line.

Յ[Ի]Շ[Ա]Տ[Ա]Կ Է ԱՐՈՒԹԻՆԻՆ, ՍՐՓՈՒԿԻՆ, Ի Դ[ՈՒ]ՆՆ ՏԱԹԵՒՈՒ ՎԱՆԻՑՆ,
ՋԵՌԱՍԲ ՕՎՍԷՓ Վ[Ա]ՐԴ[Ա]ՊԵՏԻՆ, ԹՎ[ԻՆ] ՌՄԻԵ.-ԻՆ (1776):

In memory of Arutin, Srp'uk, to the Tatev monastery, by Vardapet Ovsep', in 1776.

It is possible that Arutin and Srpuk (perhaps it is the wheedling form of the name Srбуhi) are spouses. In the abovementioned period we couldn't find Ovsep' Vardapet, who acted in the Tatev monastery. As for the Etchmiadzin's legation in the second half of the 18th century, that two persons by that name are mentioned, one of which was appointed a legate in India in 1767 and died in 1772 (Khachatryan 2004, 96), so earlier than the date of inscription and second, who was appointed a leader of diocese of Russia and legate by Simeon Yerevantsi catholicos in 1773 was the Hovsep' Arghutyan (Khachatryan 2004, 117). It is difficult to say whether Ovsep', who was testified in the inscriptions of Tatev's plates, belongs to the same Arghutyan. It should be noted that Vardapet Ovsep', who was mentioned in the inscriptions couldn't be legate but some clargyman who received the plates as a donation during his trip.

3. Copper plate, diameter 16.5 cm, diameter of bottom 8.5 cm, height 3.5 cm.

Condition – The bottom is gap. It is transformed.

Inscription – On the rim, carved letters, 1 line.

Յ[Ի]Շ[Ա]Տ[Ա]Կ ՕՎԱՆԷՍԻՆ, Ի Դ[ՈՒ]ՆԸ ՏԱԹԵՒՈՒ ՎԱՆԻՑՆ,
ՁԵՆԱՍԲ ՕՎՍԷՓ Վ[Ա]ՐԴ[Ա]ՊԵՏԻՆ, ԹՎ[ԻՆ] ՌՄԻԵ.-ԻՆ (1776):
In memory of Ovanes, to the Tatev monastery, by Vardapet Ovsep', in 1776.

4. Copper plate, diameter 17.5 cm, diameter of bottom 9.5 cm, height 4 cm.

Condition – The artefact is transformed and inclined. The tin layer partly eroded.

Inscription – On the rim, carved letters, 1 line.

Յ[Ի]Շ[Ա]Տ[Ա]Կ Է ՊԵՏՐՈՍԻՆ, Ի Դ[ՈՒ]ՆԸ ԹԱԹԵՒՈՒ ԱՌԱՔԵԼՈՒՆ, ՌՄԻԵ.-ԻՆ (1776):
In memory of Petros, to the T'at'e (T'at'eu) Apostole, in 1776.

It is very interesting evidence about the name of T'at'e Apostole, which is connected to the above-

mentioned Yevstateus, who was martyred in that place, so this inscription confirms the legend. On the north-east of the monastery is preserved a dilapidated chapel named after St. Yevstateus. According to previously abbot of monastery Bishop Artak Smbatyan, this chapel, as a sanctuary, at present hasn't importance for the pilgrims (Smbatean 1930, 279).

5. Copper plate, diameter 17 cm, diameter of bottom 10 cm, height 3.5 cm.
Condition – Satisfactory, the tin layer partly eroded.
Inscription – On the rim, carved letters, 1 line.

Յ[Ի]Շ[Ա]Տ[Ա]Կ Է ՍԻՄՈՆԻՆ, Ի Դ[ՈՒ]ՌՆ ՏԱԹԵՒՈՒ ՎԱՆԻՑՆ,
ՁԵՌԱՍՄԲ ՕՎՍԷՓ Վ[Ա]ՐԴ[Ա]ՊԵՏԻՆ, ԹՎ[ԻՆ] ՌՄԻԵ.-ԻՆ (1776):
In memory of Simon, to the Tatev monastery, by Vardapet Ovsep', in 1776.

6. Copper plate, diameter 18.5 cm, diameter of bottom 10 cm, height 3.5 cm.
Condition – The rim about 4 cm is cut, as a result of which the inscription is damaged.
Inscription – On the rim, carved letters, 1 line.

Յ[Ի]Շ[Ա]Տ[Ա]Կ Է ՏԱԼԻԹԵՒԻՆ, ՍԱՐԳԻՍԻՆ, Ի Դ[ՈՒ]ՌՆ ՏԱԹԵՒՈՒ ՎԱՆԻՑՆ,
ՁԵՌԱՍՄԲ ՕՎ[ՍԷՓ ՎԱՐԴԱՊ]ԵՏԻՆ, ԹՎ[ԻՆ] ՌՄԻԵ.-ԻՆ (1776):
In memory of Talite, Sargis, to the Tatev monastery, by Vardapet Ovsep', in 1776.

Mentioned in the inscription Talite and Sargis perhaps are also spouses. The name Talita several times was testified in written sources of the 12-15th centuries and later it is rarely (Acharyan 1962, 135).

7. Copper plate, diameter 18.5 cm, diameter of bottom 10 cm, height 3.5 cm.
Condition – The bottom is transformed.
Inscription – On the rim, carved letters, 1 line.

Յ[Ի]Շ[Ա]Տ[Ա]Կ Է ՏԻՐԱՑՈՒ ԱՐՈՒԹԻՆԻՆ, Ի Դ[ՈՒ]ՆՆ ՏԱԹԵՒՈՒ ՎԱՆԻՑՆ,
ՁԵՌԱՍԲ ՕՎՍԷՓ Վ[Ա]ՐԴ[Ա]ՊԵՏԻՆ, ԹՎ[ԻՆ] ՌՄԻԵ.-ԻՆ (1776):

In memory of sacristan Arutin, to the Tatev monastery, by Vardapet Ovsep', in 1776.

8. Copper plate, diameter 18 cm, diameter of bottom 10.5 cm, height 3 cm.

Condition – Satisfactory.

Inscription – On the external side of rim, carved and convex letters, 1 line.

Յ[Ի]Շ[Ա]Տ[Ա]Կ Է ՇՆԱԹԱՂՑԻ ՖՌԱՆԿՈՒԼԻ ՈՐԴԻ ԱՐՈՒԹԻՆ, Ի Դ[ՈՒ]ՆՆ ՏԱԹԵՒՈՒ:
In memory of Shnatagtsi Frankul's son Arut, to the Tatev monastery.

of them is dated 1775, others 1776 and one undated.

In collection there is a one plate with the same inscription too. The artefact hasn't correct date, but according to paleographic features it was also we can date to the 18th century. This inscription was also compiled by two engravers and carved part was added during the donation. Mentioned in inscription Shnatagh (or Shinatagh) village is evidenced in the new list of the tax-paying villages of Tatev monastery (Alishan 1893, 209). There are famous clergymans from this village. Bishop Hovhannes Shnatagtsi built economic buildings of monastery in the 17th century and at the beginning of 18th century Bishop Minas Shnatagtsi rebuilt

northern fortress of the same monastery and adjacent studs (Yakobson 1947, 305). At present that village is a Lernashen community of Sisian region (Hakobyan et al. 1988, 578).

Summarizing our research dedicated to the inscribed plate's collection of Tatev monastery, it should be mention the following.

The donation of plates to the Tatev monastery directly testifies the fact that this religion center functioned and had large congregation in the second half of the 18th century too. The donors wishing to deserve mentioning, besides placing khachkars in the church walls and being mentioned nominally adjacent to the carved crosses, donated as well manuscripts, bookstands, bindings,

curtains, dressing and other artefacts to the sanctuaries, among them is the church and household utensils of monastic congregation. At the request of donators are compiled the inscriptions on them, many of which passed to us as a nice evidences of the former large congregation of monasteries.

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